

Deliverable No. 6.3

DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

Grant agreement No: **633680**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the

Horizon 2020 Programme

Start date of project: **1st March 2015**

Duration: **48 months**

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Deliverable 6.3

Report on the automatic system for by-catches quantification and classification and the battery of specific fluorescent DNA probes

(Month 36)

Due date of deliverable: March 2018

Actual submission date: 27 March 2018

Dissemination Level: PU¹

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¹ PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

How to cite this document: Melado *et al.*, 2018. Report on the automatic system for by-catches quantification and classification and the battery of specific fluorescent DNA probes, (Horizon 2020 DiscardLess Report Deliverable D6.3), Zenodo doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3265844](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3265844)

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Summary of D6.3.

Report on the automatic system for by-catches quantification and classification and the battery of specific fluorescent DNA probes.

This document is the third deliverable in work package six (WP6) of the DiscardLess project, which aims to contribute to the gradual elimination of the discards in the European fisheries, in agreement with the reformed Common Fisheries Policy of the EU and the implementation of the Landing Obligation (LO). LO states that all species with Total Allowable Catches (TAC) or Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) have to be classified, quantified and landed. Each species must be separated in different boxes, but also fishes under MCRS have to be separated as the LO states that their use for direct human consumption is not allowed.

This increases the need of onboard handling, that is already very time consuming and demanding, and therefore will need the introduction of innovative solutions for the identification, classification and quantification of catches.

The work package deals with two possible solutions for the identification, classification and quantification of catches. On the one hand, automatic systems for the quantification and classification of the catches has been developed and, on the other hand, fast DNA probes identification of several species has been established.

Box 1: Report Highlights

The LO implies the mandatory classification and quantification of all catches of species with TAC/quotas or MCRS. These changes suppose an important increase of on-board labour effort needed.

To simplify the on-board procedure a bulk landing of by-catches is proposed and the establishment of a custom in the harbour for the classification and quantification of by-catches.

To ease this procedure the use of automatic classification and quantification systems is proposed and with this scope an artificial vision system has been developed,

On the other hand, the identification of species when stored in bulk, or if silage is produced, may become difficult. To avoid the inclusion of species with quota or TAC mixed with other species, easy and fast system for their identification are needed.

With this aim fast and portable DNA methods have been developed.

Box 2: The methods/approaches followed

- Development of an automatic system for the quantification and classification in land of the by-catch when these are landed in mixed bulk through artificial vision technology.
- Design of a PCR and Sequencing tool to obtaining an immediate on-site control of the presence/absence of valuable fish and/or non-compliance discards in the value chain, which can be operated by less qualified personal in an industrial environment.

Box 3: How these results can be used and by who?

- If the bulk landing is accepted, these results will be of great profit for fishermen and their association.
- The development of automatic systems for the classification and quantification can be of great interest on board if legally accepted.
- The use of fast DNA identification of fish species can be of interest for the regulation fulfilment
- These methods can also be of interest to avoid fraud in the identification of catches.

Box 4: Policy Recommendations

- Change in policies are needed to allow the bulk storage on-board, the establishment of by-catches customs in the harbours and the use of automated quantification and classification systems.
- The use of on-board technology for the classification and quantification of by-catches, and even all catches, can be of interest once the discards are forbidden.
- The improvement of traceability requirement may boost the use of system such as de fast DNA method developed.

Abbreviations	
CFP	Common Fishery Policy
EU	European Union
FOV	Field of View
LO	Landing Obligation
MCRS	Minimum Conservation Reference Size
ROI	Region of Interest
UUC	Unavoidable, Unwanted Catches
WP	Work Package
TAC	Total Allowable Catches

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1 Introduction

The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) of the European Commission introduced in 2013 a discard ban which states that all catches of species subjected to catch quotas and/or Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS) will have to be landed and will be counted against quota.

The discard ban, or Landing Obligation (LO), is being gradually implemented, since 2015 to 2019 when all EU fisheries will be required to land all catches. Meanwhile, involved agents may explore and put into practice different strategies first, to minimize the discards and second, to find the most adequate uses for unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC) subjected to the landing obligation in order to prevent the impact that the LO may have in the harbours and local economies.

This report is the third deliverable in work package six (WP6) of the DiscardLess project, which deals with the impacts and challenges that the new politics may cause in land.

To evaluate and overcome the possible challenges, the following specific objectives are addressed in this WP:

- 1) Analysing the potential availability of UUC in specific harbours;
- 2) Evaluating most suitable uses of UUC;
- 3) Constructing an initial selection of potential uses and solution approach;
- 4) Ensuring traceability and market acceptance of the products resulting from UUC valorisation;
- 5) Obtaining a clear and convincing picture of the economic profile and the feasibility of the implementation of the proposed solutions;
- 6) Validating the solution proposed for best use of UUC by a pilot trial;

This current deliverable D6.3 deals with establishing full traceability and operational monitoring systems at any step of the value chain.

First, an **automatic system** has been developed **for the quantification and classification at land** of the bycatch when these are landed in mixed bulk. An innovative artificial vision technology has been designed and tested and a full design of its up-scaling and linking with conveyor belts and electrically or pneumatically activated devices for the physical separation of the catch depending on their size and species performed.

Second, an **alternative use of species identity molecular methods** is developed, complementing the fully documented genetic methods developed in 5.3 with a quicker and simpler, but slightly less accurate alternative tool with a different purpose. Based on Real Time PCR and Sequencing, this tool aims at obtaining an immediate on-site control of the presence of valuable fish and/or non-compliance discards in the value chain, which can be operated by less qualified personal in an industrial environment. The tool will also be used to calibrate and validate the automatic classification system. Task 6.4 will interlink with Task 5.3.

2 Automatic classification system: probe of concept

Due to the banning of discard, the amount of catches that will have to be handled on board will increase dramatically, and the related costs will impact in the fisheries results. The possibility of including new classification technologies on board is limited by legislation and therefore other solutions have to be developed.

One possibility is the bulk landing of by-catches in a sort of custom located in the landing harbours that will count, quantify and allocate the by-catches to its quotas. However, this procedure needs also the implementation of automated classification systems to be able to cope with the landings in an appropriate time.

Some researchers have proposed methods for fish classification using machine vision (Dowlati 2012², Jin Hu 2012³). Storbeck and Daan (2001)⁴ developed a fish species recognition system (for cod, whiting, dab, plaice and sole) by computer vision and a neural network program. The vision system measures several fish features, including width and height at various locations along the body of the fish as seen by a camera located perpendicular to a conveyor belt. White et al. (2006)⁵ described trials of computer vision machine (The Catch Meter) for identifying and measuring different species of flatfish by means of moment-invariant method in which the fish are transported along a conveyor underneath a digital camera. Additionally, many trials have recently been conducted using Fully Documented Fisheries and CCTV systems onboard fishing vessels (cf. DiscardLess deliverable 5.3).

Under this work, a probe of concept for the automatic classification and quantification of by-catches at shore, based on online computer vision was designed, trained and tested. The aim of the preliminary trial was the discrimination of 6 different fish species, which were selected for being the most common in discards in the Bay of Biscay (BoB). The 6 species were horse mackerel, blue whiting, small hake, mackerel, anchovy and sardine.

² Majid Dowlati, Seyed Saeid Mohtasebi, Miguel de la Guardia. Application of machine-vision techniques to fish-quality assessment, *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, Vol. 40, 2012

³ Jing Hu, Daoliang Li, Qingling Duan, Yueqi Han, Guifen Chen, Xiuli Si. Fish species classification by color, texture and multi-class support vector machine using computer vision. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 88 (2012) 133–140

⁴ Frank Storbeck, Berent Daan. Fish species recognition using computer vision and a neural network. *Fisheries Research* 51 (2001)

⁵ D.J. White, C. Svellingen, N.J.C. Strachan. Automated measurement of species and length of fish by computer vision. *Fisheries Research* 80 (2006) 203–210

2.1 Methods

2.1.1 Samples selection and characterization

The selection of the species of study was made by an analysis of the main discards that appear in the trawling fleets in the BoB in the northern part of Spain, reported in the deliverable 6.1. Six species were defined as preliminary target for the pilot: horse mackerel, blue whiting, small hake, mackerel, anchovy and sardine.

For the preliminary characterization and parametrization of the species, the characteristic features of each specie were defined: length, colour, width, contour, fin number and position, eyes and mouth position, anatomic specificities, etcetera.

2.1.2 Equipment

The online classification system consists of:

- Blue conveyor belt.
- Illumination
- Camera
- Computer hardware
- Image capture board
- Software

All these parts were connected to perform the pilot trial and the full system was tested.

2.1.2.1 Illumination

Illumination has a great influence in the image quality. A good illumination helps to improve the success of the image processing and analysis due to the noise reduction and the enhancement of the image contrast. Thus, the position, types of lamps and colour of the illumination were considered carefully to obtain the best images.

In this case, two types of light sources were used (Figure 1 and Figure 2):

- i) White illumination, composed by two LED light bars of 305 x 25 cm.
- ii) Infrared illumination, composed by two LED bars of 305 x 25 cm.

Figure 1. White and infrared illumination bars

Figure 2. Illumination bars installed on the classification system

This lamp selection allowed to get good results in the visible and infrared spectrum enhancing the possibilities of image analysis.

2.1.2.2 Camera

A multispectral camera (400-1000 nm), JAI AD-130 GE was used. It has Digital 2CCD (Figure 3) progressive scan, with resolution of 1296 x 966 pixels. It has two types of sensors: colour sensor output and monochrome NIR sensor, which can be set at synchronous (SYNC) or asynchronous (ASYN) (Figure 4).

Working with both types of images, allows to detect several features that would be impossible to be identified with only one type of image. For example, the segmentation of the fish from the background was done using the multispectral NIR image, since when the conveyor belt was stained with fish blood and fish waste, it was impossible to segment only with the RGB image. Nevertheless, some other features, like the fins position, were detected better with the RGB images.

Figure 3. CCD sensors scheme

Visible Response AD-130 GE

Near-IR Response AD-130 GE

Figure 4. Multispectral camera and visible and NIR responses

2.1.2.3 Hardware

Image acquisition and processing are very demanding tasks, and the speed of the system can be limited by the response of the hardware. It is therefore of paramount importance the correct sizing and configuring of the hardware.

The hardware used consisted of:

- a) Two industrial PC Platform NY-series equipments were used for image acquisition. It consists of 3 processors: Intel Core i7-4700EQ Processor 4th generation CPU with Fan Unit for active cooling, Intel Core i5-4300U Processor 4th generation CPU with fan-less cooling and Intel Celeron 2980U Processor 4th generation CPU with fan-less cooling. It can accomplish both high speed and high precision. It has two operating systems: Windows and Real-Time OS. It can currently perform both machine controls by using the Controller function on the Real-Time OS and the

application processing on Windows. They can run independently and may exchange data one with each other while each makes an independent operation.

- b) A C6650-0050 Control Cabinet Industrial PC (Beckhoff) server, for image processing (Figure 5).

c)

Figure 5. A. industrial PC Platform NY-series; B. C6650-0050 Control Cabinet Industrial PC (Beckhoff) server; C. Assembly of the systems

2.1.2.4 Image capture board

The image capture board allows the visualization of the acquired images.

The capture board is able to detect the presence of fish with no need of a photocell nor encoder in the conveyor belt. The camera can detect the presence of the sample in the field of view (FOV) and tracks it until it is centred in the image, just under the camera.

Figure 6. Image capture board

2.1.2.5 Software

The software is programmed using:

- c#: used for the interface.
- Hdev HALCON: it is a specific software, used in the industry. It consists of several computer vision toolboxes for image acquisition, processing, segmentation and feature extraction.
- WEKA (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis). It is used for machine learning and data mining.

The acquisition and processing software consists of several modules with different functions:

- Alarm module.** Allows to set up the alarms limits.
- Acquisition module.** It corrects the lense aberrations and acquires and corrects the images, so to improve the success of the processing. When the sample is larger than the field of view (FOV) it acquires several images and reconstruct and rescales them. In this module, the segmentation is of the image from the background is made and the defined features are extracted to be submitted to image analysis.

Figure 7. Acquisition module

- **Vision module.** In this module, the image analysis algorithms are applied, and several parameters are calculated from the segmented image.

Figure 8. Vision module

- **Training module.** Once the image is segmented and the features are extracted, the model is trained using WEKA. Training is made supervised. For training a robust model, a lot of samples are needed. Thus, a preliminary model is built with several samples and then, the model will learn with the new samples.

Figure 9. Training module

- **Calibration module (Figure 10).** To avoid problems of chromatic aberrations, a chromatic pattern (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Calibration module

Figure 11. Chromatic calibration pattern

Figure 12. Spatial calibration pattern

- **WCF communication module.** This module allows remote communication to send the results to a data base.

2.1.3 Image processing

Image processing is made according to the following steps (Figure 11):

Figure 13. Image processing methodology

2.1.3.1 Image acquisition

Since the camera has four types of detectors (3 sensors for RGB and 1 for NIR), two different types of images were acquired:

- RGB (Figure 13A): analysed in three different colour spaces: RGB and HSV.
- Multispectral (Figure 13B): grayscale image.

Figure 14. A. RGB image of blue whiting. B. NIR image (700-1000 nm) of blue whiting

2.1.3.2 Image pre-processing

Before feature extraction and analysis, images need to be pre-processed to reduce noise and to facilitate the segmentation procedure. There are several techniques, but the ones that best results gave in this case were: image enhancement, noise filtering and edge detection.

- Image enhancement: it accentuates image features, such as edges, boundaries and contrast. It does not increase the information of the original image, but it increases the dynamic range of the chosen features, which eases its detection.
- Noise filtering: a filter is used to reduce the unnecessary information and noise from the image.
- Edge detection: it determines where boundaries of objects fall within an image.

2.1.3.3 Image segmentation

Afterwards, the images are segmented. A region of interest (ROI) is selected, in this case, the pixels belonging to the fish. All the pixels that do not belong to the selected ROI (background) are removed. The result is a binary image, where all the pixels belonging to the ROI will have value 1, and the rest 0.

2.1.3.4 Feature extraction

Feature extraction was based on the study of the morphologic and grey level characteristics. All the features were extracted from the grayscale NIR images and the R, G, B, H, S and V channels.

These features are related to morphologic parameters, gray levels and colour.

- **Morphologic:** morphologic features are related to the shape characteristics of an object. There are different approaches for shape feature study, but a very popular one is to equate the segmented ROIs to rectangles and/or ellipses and to study them with the typical parameters of such figures (Rosin, 1999⁶). From all the features that exist in image processing, some were selected because they are good descriptors of fish shape. The selected parameters were:
 - Major axis (R_a) / Minor axis (R_b) of the equivalent ellipsis. The segmented object is considered as an ellipsis. Thus, the major axis (the one which passes through the center of mass of the segmented fish) and the minor axis (which also passes through the centre of mass of the segmented image and is perpendicular to the major axis) are calculated (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Major axis (R_a) and minor axis (R_b) of the equivalent ellipsis in the segmented image.

- Ellipsis parameters: anisometry, bulkiness, structure factor.
- Circularity. It is the degree to which the segmented object (the fish) is similar to a circle, taking into account the smoothness of the perimeter. It is a dimensionless value, defined by the expression:

$$C = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi A}{P^2}}$$

Where A is the area of the circle and P the perimeter.

As a shape becomes more round and smooth, the circularity value would approach one.

⁶ Rosin, P.L, 1999. Measuring rectangularity. Machine Vision and Applications, 11(4), 191-196.

- Compactness. It measures the efficiency with which a boundary encloses an area. It is defined by the expression:

$$C(s) = \frac{A}{\frac{P^2}{4\pi}}$$

Where A is the area and P the perimeter. $C(s) = 1$ is the maximum compactness. Low values of $C(s)$ are related to highly elongated shapes.

- Roundness. It is defined by the expression:

$$R = \frac{4A}{\pi R_a^2}$$

Where A is the area and R_a the major axis.

- Convexity. It is a value that measures the convexity of a figure. Its values are between $[0,1]$, being 1 the value of a convex set. For determining the convexity, the convex hull polygon (CH) is used.
- Rectangularity. It is a very useful shape descriptor that has been applied in industrial inspection and discrimination of fish (Richards and Esteves, 1997⁷).
- Moments: they provide invariant measures of shape (Kotoulas and Andreadis, 2005⁸).
 - Geometrical moments: PSI1, PSI2, PSI3, PSI4.
 - Invariant moments to translations and linear transformations.
 - Geometrical moments of the ROI: M11, M21, M12, M20, M02, M03, M30.
 - Scaled moments.
 - Scale invariants.
- **Gray levels:**
 - Mean Gray: mean value of the gray pixels from the ROI.
 - Deviation gray: Deviation of the gray values from the ROI.
 - Gray plane deviation: Deviation of the gray values, computed from the approximation of the gray values to a plane.
 - Entropy gray: Entropy gray is a texture feature that measures the randomness that can be used to characterize the texture of the input image. Anisotropy gray
 - Entropy Fuzzy Gray
 - Perimeter fuzzy gray: It is used to determine the differences of fuzzy belonging between a point of view and the image of its neighbours.
 - Energy0, Correlation0, Homogeneity0, Contrast0, Energy45, Correlation45, Homogeneity45, Contrast45, Energy90, Correlation90, Homogeneity90, Contrast90, Energy135, Correlation135, Homogeneity135, Contrast135: Cooccurrence matrix of the grayscale image, computed at 0, 45, 90 and 135 degrees.

⁷ R.A. Richards and C. Esteves. Use of scale morphology for discriminating wild stocks of atlantic striped bass. Trans. Amer. Fisheries Soc., 127(6):919–925, 1997

⁸ L Kotoulas, I Andreadis, 2005. Image analysis using moments. 5th Int. Conf. on Technology and Automation, Thessaloniki, Greece 360364

- Cooccurrence matrix of the gray image, at 0, 45, 90 and 135 grades.

2.1.3.5 Model training

For building the model, 5 supervised classifiers, based on machine learning algorithms are used: 4 for classification of the species and 1 for outlier detection. The scheme of the classification model can be seen in Figure 14.

- Two decision trees:
 - JRip
 - J48
- Naïve Bayes. It is a probabilistic classifier, based on Bayes' theorem.
- Artificial Neural Network: multilayer perceptron (MLP), which is feedforward that consists of at least three layers of nodes. Each node is a neuron that uses a nonlinear activation function, except for the input nodes. It uses backpropagation for training.
- KNN. It is a non-parametric method. An object will belong to the major category of its neighbours.

Figure 16. Classification model scheme

2.1.3.6 Model validation

Model validation was performed by introducing in the system several unknown samples. For model performance, the confusion matrix was computed. Confusion matrix allows the visualization of performance of a classification algorithm. Each row of the matrix represents the instances in a predicted class and the column represents the ones in an actual class. Thus, it can be seen how many fish are being categorized as another class and which is that class.

2.2 Results and discussion

2.2.1 Morphological characteristics

Figure 17. Parameters and features analysed

2.2.1.1 European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

Figure 18. European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

Body: It has a large, thin, soft body, slightly, compressed laterally. It has flat head and big, hollow eyes. In the lower jaw it has two rows of teeth and in the upper jaw, one row. The inner part of the mouth is black. The lateral line is almost straight and parallel to the dorsal line.

Fins: It has two dorsal fins: the first one is shorter and has 8-11 radii and the second one, which is long and low-cut in its medium area, has 35-40 radii. The anal fin is long and has 36-40 radii and it begins at the same level than the second dorsal fin. Pectoral fins are also long and short.

Finally, the pelvic fins are in a very anterior position, ahead of the pectorals. The caudal fin is somewhat forked.

Size: From 80 to 130 cm and from 2 to 10 kg.

Colour: It is brown or blackish in the upper part, gray in the flanks and silver in the ventral region. In trawl hake, the back is more gray than in the longline, due to the loss of scale. Also, longline hake usually has a greater amount of superficial mucus.

2.2.1.2 *Horse mackerel (Trachurus trachurus)*

Figure 19. Black mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*)

Body: Long, fusiform, slightly compressed with sharp front profile. It has small fins and a lateral line on the dorsal anterior part, which goes from the operculum to the end of the first dorsal bony fin where it descends abruptly until the half of the body. The lateral fins (64-76) are big and pointy. It also has an accessory lateral line from the first dorsal fin until the ratios 23-31 of the second dorsal. Big eyes with a developed, adipose eyelid.

Fins: It has two dorsal fins, the first one with 8 hard radii (the first one is slightly separated from the rest), and the second one with a hard radius and 29-33 soft ones. The anal fin has 2 hard radius. Behind them they have 1 hard radius and 24-29 soft radius, slightly separated.

Size: The maximum size is 60 cm. Nevertheless, the captured specimens do not exceed 30 cm long.

Color: The head and back color is gray or bluish green, with a black small stain on the top edge of the operculus. The flanks and the abdomen are lighter, with silver reflection.

2.2.1.3 Mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*)

Figure 20. Mackerel - *Scomber scombrus*.

Body: Long and slightly compressed, covered by tiny scales.

Fins: Both dorsal fins are separated. The first one, with 10-13 bones and the second one with 11-13 soft radius. The anal fin has 1 bone and 11-13 soft raidus. Behind the second dorsal and the anal fin there are 5 pins. The caudal fin is bifurcated, with two small bottoms in the base of each lobule.

Size: It can last 50 cm y 50 kg of weight. Nevertheless, normally it is around 30 cm long and 250-300 grams weighth.

Color: Back color is greenish blue, with dark transversal lines. The lateral and ventral bottom parts are white.

2.2.1.4 Blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*)

Figure 21. Blue whiting - *Micromesistius poutassou*.

Body: It has long body, big mouth, with the lower jaw slightly longer than the top one. The lateral line reaches the caudal peduncule. It has sensorial channels connected to the head by means several pores.

Fins: It has three dorsal fins with soft radius (12-14 the first two and 23-28 the third one), with space between them, especially between the last two. There are two anal fins: the first one begins at the first dorsar fin and ends at the third one, with 33 to 39 radii; the second one, has 24-27 radius. The caudal fin is forked. It is bluish gray, lighter in the ventral zone and practically black in the base of the pectoral fins and in the opercula.

Size: it can reach 50 cm long, but the normal size is 15-30 cm long.

Color: The back is bluish gray, with silver edges and white abdomen. The pectoral fins and the opercula are dark.

2.2.1.5 *Sardine (Sardina pilchardus)*

Figure 22. Sardine - *Sardina pilchardus*.

Body: It has a long oval body. Its caudal fin is bifurcated. Scales are big, thin and slightly descendent, with no scales in the head: 30 along half of the body. The gill opercule has specific radial marks (3-5). The eyes have eyelids and has a prominent lower jaw.

Fins: Dorsal fin is short, with 17-18 radius and it is inserted near the head. The anal fin also has 17-18 radius, but the last two are longer than the rest of them. The pelvic fin has 8 radii and are inserted under the dorsal fin.

Size: It can last 30 cm long maximum. The normal size is 15-20 cm long.

Color: Lateral color is from blue to olive green with a silvery abdomen. It has a bluish shine.

2.2.1.6 *Anchovy (Engraulis encrasicolus)*

Figure 23. Anchovy - *Engraulis encrasicolus*.

Body: Small thin oval fish. The ventral size is not saw, which differentiates it from other cupleidae. Scales fall easily. It has a pointy snout and the corner of the mout is behind the eyes. It has no lateral line.

Fins: The only dorsal fin, with 15-18 radius, is in the half of the body. The anal fin, with 20-26 radius, starts at the beginning of the dorsal fin. It has two big scales near the caudal fin. The pelvic fins are at the beginning of the dorsal one. The caudal fin is bifurcated.

Size: 9-20 cm long.

Color: The dorsal color is from greenish blue to light gray. The flanks are silvery and are surrounded by a dark line. The ventral zone is light and the caudal fin borders are slightly dark.

2.2.2 Weight estimation

Weight (W) can be calculated from the size (L), using this expression:

$$W = (a L)^b$$

the parameter a and *b* of each species are summarized in Table 1, and the weight (W) is obtained in grams when the size is expressed in millimetres.

“a” is a coefficient related to body form and *b* is an exponent indicating isometric growth when equal to 3.

Table 1. Values of *a* and *b* for each species

Specie	a	b
Horse mackerel	5.75E-06	3.048
Small hake	2.37E-06	3.174
Anchovy	6.27E-07	3.465
Blue whiting	6.71E-06	2.993
Mackerel	2.40E-06	3.187
Sardine	2.52E-06	3.217

2.2.3 Results on classification

The preliminary calibration/validation was made using a sample of fish N=120, distributed as follows:

Anchovy: n=20;

Blue whiting: n=20;

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Horse Mackerel: n=20;

Small hake: n=20;

Sardine: n=20;

Mackerel: n=20;

For the trial a mix of selected fishes were used, including an “unknow” fraction.

All the data were divided into two subsets: a calibration (50%) and a test data set (50%). Calibration set was used to train the algorithms in a supervised and then, the classification was tested using the test set.

Figure 24. Sample for a trial of classification.

All the fish were put randomly in the conveyor belt at 12 m/min speed, and they were classified in real time, with a 90 % of accuracy of the classification. Table 2 and Table 3 show the results of the classification and the confusion matrix.

Table 2. True positive and false negative classification rates

Species	True positive rate (%)	False negative rate (%)
Anchovy	90	10
Blue whiting	100	0
Horse mackerel	90	10
Small hake	95	5
Sardine	87	13
Mackerel	67	33

Table 3. Confusion matrix of the classification

		Predicted class					
		Anchovy	Blue whiting	Black mackerel	Small hake	Sardine	Mackerel
True class	Anchovy	90 %	0 %	5 %	5 %	0 %	0 %
	Blue whiting	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
	Horse mackerel	0 %	0 %	90 %	10 %	0 %	0 %
	Small hake	0 %	5 %	0 %	95 %	0 %	0 %
	Sardine	0 %	0 %	13 %	0 %	87 %	0 %
	Mackerel	0 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	0 %	67 %

Systems with this configuration allow to evaluate more than 10 kg in less than 10 min. The classification speed is highly dependent on the size of the fish as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Estimated classification speed for catches with a size equal to 75 % of MCRS

Specie	MCRS (mm)	L (mm)	W (g)	kg/min
Horse mackerel	150	112,5	10,3	0,93
Small hake	270	202,5	49,6	2,67
Anchovy	120	90	3,7	0,40
Blue whiting	150	112,5	9,2	0,84
Mackerel	200	150	20,7	1,46
Sardine	110	82,5	3,7	0,43

2.2.4 Up-scaling and design

Several improvements of the system have been evaluated to design and scale-up the classification and quantification robot.

On the one hand, the system can be used at a higher speed of the conveyor belt up to 60 m/min and minimizing the separation between samples, increasing the processing speed 6 folds.

Also, a system with four parallel way has been designed (Figure 25). Once landed in bulk, the catches are loaded in the system by an automated container dumper. Then the catches are elevated by a dosage conveyor (2) and put in a V shaped slide that help the fish to accommodate in the correct direction.

As fish is a difficult material to handle, further separation and accommodation is foreseen in a vibration belt (2). Then, discards drop in a further conveyor with higher speed to separate the pieces and make them go through the “artificial vision system” for the identification and quantification. This conveyor has to be provided with an encoder that will indicate the position of the discard once it leaves the vision system, to activate one or another selection palette (6) that will drop the catch to a final conveyor up to its storage.

Figure 25. Design of a four-way system. 1- Material reception and lifter conveyor. 2- Vibrating conveyor 3- Classification conveyor with encoder. 4- Conveyor of sorted fish. 5- Reception boxes. 6. Mechanical Actuators. 7- Bulk fish loader.

With this configuration the system may be able to classify up to 14 kg/min of discards. Again, the result is highly dependent on the size of the catches and its distribution. The smaller the fishes are, the smaller the classification speed expressed in kg/min of the system is. Moreover, with a speed of 60 m/min and small fish the systems must be able to process up to 10 units per second, that would require high performance hardware.

The performance of this system with catches above MCRS is much higher as the weigh/size ratio increases significantly.

To maximise the speed of each lane, a mechanic size classifier can be set up on the top of the lifter conveyor, so each conveyor can be adjusted to the maxima classification speed.

For example, in Figure 26 the speed of classification is shown for 2 different conveyor speeds and expressed as kg/min that can be classified and unit/s processed. Supposing that the artificial vision system could identify 2 units per second, hakes under MRCS couldn't be processed with the conveyor with a 60 m/s speed while they would easily be handled at 15 m/s.

Figure 26. Classification speed. Triangles are values in kg/min (right axis). Circles are values in unit/s (left axis). Filled markers are for a conveyor speed of 60 m/s and empty markers are for a 30 m/s and dashed markers 15 m/s. Red line indicates the MCRS of hake.

2.3 Conclusions

The morphological parameters of each fish species were defined and selected. Then, an on-line classification prototype, based on computer vision, was built and tested, providing successful results, with an accuracy of 90 %, of 6 different fish species, at 12 m/min.

These results are acceptable as a probe of concept, but still, several aspects have to be improved such as:

- the increase of the processing speed
- the segmentation of several objects in the field of view

This System can be up-scaling with the integration of several lines in a compact system allowing to process big quantities of by catches. The possibilities for this system in an inland custom are very interesting and can help to recover the greatest value of the different kinds of discards.

On the other hand, with an increase of speed and a compact design, this technology can be adapted to its implementation on board for a full classification and quantification of all the catches and by-catches, allowing a faster and accurate handling. This would also lead to the possibility of rapid return to the sea for species with high survival rate. However, this option needs the adaptation of the policies to this new scenario.

3 Fast DNA identification of species

Fish species identification methodologies are generally based on DNA fragment detection by Real Time PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction), PCR-Sequencing, etcetera. These methods, based on the thermal amplification of nucleic acids fragments by PCR, has revealed as one of the most successful and extensively used methods in the identification of fish species.

However, the PCR technique has its limitations, such as requiring precise temperature control and rapid thermocycling steps among the temperatures of dissociation (95 °C), annealing (55-65 °C) and elongation (70 °C). Moreover, PCR based identification methodologies are always very reliable, but the downside is that, generally, it takes several days to obtain a conclusive result and it must be carried out by high qualified personal in control laboratories.

As a matter of fact, these methods are not easy to be implemented as routine and immediate on-site control of the presence of valuable fish and/or non-compliance discards in the value chain. For that reason, the use of other enzymes to mimic DNA replication *in vivo* has recently emerged as a solution to conventional PCR polymerases.

At the moment, three main isothermal amplification reactions have been described for DNA amplification: loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), nicking enzyme amplification reaction (NEAR) and helicase-dependent amplification (HDA). However, these techniques require an initial denaturation step at 95 °C (HDA and NEAR) or need complex primers design.

To solve these drawbacks an innovative isothermal amplification called recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) offers interesting advantages. This technique facilitates the binding of oligonucleotide primers to template DNA. Primers are elongated by a strand-displacing DNA Bsu polymerase while single-stranded DNA-binding proteins stabilise amplification reaction intermediates.

Compared to other amplification enzymes, Bsu polymerase maintains similar activity in inhibiting environments, requires a shorter incubation time, operates at lower temperatures, is easy to use and the amplified products do not need post-amplification treatment. All of these characteristics make the application of RPA methods for rapid and on-site detection of fish species very attractive.

In fact, RPA technology enables the identification of fish species in less than an hour, including DNA isolation step. This rapid and portable technology enables fish authentication to make point of use decisions on the industry. Moreover, these on-site tools can be operated by less qualified personal in an industrial environment with an inexpensive, portable and very simple to use small equipment, with little or no hardware required. Consequently, these tools could be used in-, on-, by- or at-line in various locations of the food supply chain for control the industrial discards of valuable fish species

In order to evaluate the applicability of RPA technology to identify the presence of valuable commercial fish species in this industrial environment, we have selected two remarkable cases studies (Atlantic Cod and European Hake) very important for Icelandic and Basque fishing sector, respectively.

3.1 Methodology

The development of the RPA probes includes 4 steps:

- Sample preparation
- DNA isolation
- Primers and probes design
- RPA assay

Test of identification of selectivity and detection limits has been performed to design a fast, reliable and easy to use system.

3.1.1 Sample preparation

The Gadoid specimens were obtained from AZTI's tissue collection. Binary fish mixed samples were prepared by homogenizing 25 g of white muscle with a blender.

Several other species, named in Table 5, were also used for different purposes during the experimentation.

Table 5: Codification, scientific name and English name correspondance

3A_CODE	Scientific name	English name
ALK	Theragra chalcogramma	Alaska pollock
BLI	Molva dypterygia	Blue ling
COD	Gadus morhua	Atlantic cod
GRC	Gadus ogac	Greenland cod
HAD	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Haddock
HKE	Merluccius merluccius	European hake
HKK	Merluccius capensis	Shallow-water Cape hake
LIN	Molva molva	Ling
PCO	Gadus macrocephalus	Pacific cod
POK	Pollachius virens	Saithe
POL	Pollachius pollachius	Pollack
USK	Brosme brosme	Tusk
WHB	Micromesistius poutassou	Blue whiting
WHG	Merlangius merlangus	Whiting

3.1.2 DNA isolation

For DNA isolation from fish samples, 10-25 mg were excised with a scalpel. The tissue was mixed with 300 μ L extraction buffer (1 % (w/v) SDS, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM EDTA, Tris-HCl pH 8.0) supplemented with 40 μ L 5 M guanidine thiocyanate, 50 μ L proteinase K (600 U/mL) and subsequently incubated at 56 (\pm 5) $^{\circ}$ C overnight. After centrifugation for 5 min at 16,000 g the supernatant was purified using the Wizard DNA Clean-Up System (Promega Biotech). Rapid DNA extraction were carried with DNAzol (Invitrogen) following the specifications of manufacturer.

3.1.3 Primers and probes design

Consensus mitochondrial cytochrome b region were obtained after comparing 87 cod sequences obtained from AZTI and GenBank database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). Cod consensus region was subsequently compared with 88 sequences belong to 16 different gadoid species from a variety of genus (*Pollachius*, *Gadus*, *Molva*, *Merluccius* etc...) by BLAST (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).

In the case of European hake 35 *Merluccius spp.* sequences belong to mitochondrial d-loop region were scrutinized. Hake consensus region was compared with other gadoid species by BLAST. Cod and hake discriminatory polymorphisms were selected as targets and primers and TwistAmp Exo- and Nfo-probes were designed according to the guidelines of TwistDX (Figure 27). Exo-probes presented homology to the target amplicon that contains a basic nucleotide analogue (H: tetrahydrofuran residue; THF) which replaces a nucleotide in a target sequence flanked by a dT-fluorophore (F: FAM) and a corresponding dT-quencher group (Q) (these replacing T sequences found with the corresponding target sequence).

In addition, probe is blocked from any potential polymerase extension by a suitable 3'-modification group (Spacer-C3). The reverse Nfo-primer was labelled with a biotin at the 5' end, and the Nfo-probes was designed to add a 5' fluorescein FAM, an internal THF and a Spacer-C3 on the 3' end. Probes and primers were synthesized by DNA Technologies. Self-annealing evaluation between primers and probes were carried out with the software Oligo Analyzer 1.2 (Integrated DNA Technologies).

Figure 27. Schematic RPA Exo and Nfo detection systems

3.1.4 RPA assay

RPA assays were carried out in a total volume of 50 μ L using the TwistAmp Exo kit or TwistAmp Nfo kit (TwistDX, Cambridge, UK). Reactions contained 10 μ M of specific reverse and forward primer, 10 μ M of a specific TwistAmp Exo Probe, 1-20 ng of genomic DNA (isolated following previous protocol), 14 mM of Mg acetate, and 1 \times rehydration buffer. First, all the reagents except for the DNA template and Mg acetate were prepared in a master mix, which was distributed into each 0.2 mL reaction tube containing the enzyme and the nucleotides in a dried pellet. Then, DNA was added into the tubes, and Mg acetate was dispensed lastly. Since the RPA reaction starts as soon as magnesium is added, the tubes were immediately placed into a portable T8 isothermal device (TwistDX, Cambridge, UK) at 39-42 $^{\circ}$ C for 15-20 min (Figure 28). In the case of Nfo-probes the amplified products were detected by lateral flow strip (Millennia Hybriditech).

Figure 28. Portable T8 isothermal device (TwistDX, Cambridge, UK)

3.2 Results

This study investigates RPA technology to discriminate between cod and hake from other gadoid specie.

3.2.1 Cod RPA assay

The pair of primers successfully amplified a short diagnostic DNA fragment of 109 base pairs (bp) belong to mitochondrial cytochrome b gene DNA fragment. The specificity and reproducibility of the RPA Exo system has also been successfully evaluated. Figure 29 shows the specificity of the RPA Exo-probe to discriminate between cod and other gadoids. Amplification curve is visible after only 5 minutes.

Figure 29. COD (*Gadus morhua*) specificity RPA Exo-assay. A number of individuals (n) of different gadoid species; ALK: *Theragra chalcogramma* (n=5); WHG: *Merlangius merlangius* (n=3); PCO: *Gadus macrocephalus* (n=2); GRC: *Gadus ogac* (n=2); LIN: *Molva molva* (n=4); HAD: *Melanogrammus aeglefinus* (n=5); WHB: *Micromesistius poutasou* (n=3) POK: *Pollachius virens* (n=5); BLI: *Molva dypterygia* (n=3); POL: *Pollachius pollachius* (n=4); USK: *Brosme brosme* (n=3). Non Template Control (NTC). Y-axis indicates fluorescence units (mV) and X-axis the time (minutes)

According with the type of discards that we are likely to find mixtures of fish species in blocks, a batch of binary samples [COD + HKK (*Merluccius capensis*)] at different proportion were tested. Finally, we can conclude that the RPA Exo-assay is able to identify the presence of 5 % of cod in a complex mixture of fish muscle (Figure 30).

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Figure 30. COD (*Gadus morhua*) limit of detection RPA Exo-assay in six different binary samples (95 % HKK: 5 % COD) Non Template Control (NTC). Y-axis indicates fluorescence units and X-axis the time (minutes). HKK: *Merluccius capensis*

In order to simplify the assay, we have optimized a RPA Nfo-assay in a lateral flow format. In the Figure 31A is shown a lateral flow with a clear detectable positive test line (COD). No cross-detection was observed with the DNA isolated from other gadoid fish species. Finally, the limit of detection of this assay was also 5 % (Figure 31B).

Figure 31. **(A)** Cod specificity RPA Nfo-assay **(B)** Cod limit of detection RPA Nfo-assay with five binary samples. COD: *Gadus morhua*. HKK: *Merluccius capensis*. Test line (T); Internal Control line (C). Negative Template Control (NTC)

3.2.2 Hake RPA assay

The pair of primers successfully amplified a diagnostic DNA fragment of 196 bp belong to mitochondrial control region. Because of the results of previous cod detection system, in the case of hake, we have directly optimized a RPA Nfo-assay in a lateral flow format. In the Figure 32 A1 and A2 is shown a lateral flow with a clear detectable positive test line (HKE). No cross-detection was observed with the DNA isolated from other gadoid fish species (for example *Pollachius pollachius*). However, some cases of cross detection line were observed with some *Merluccius* species like *Merluccius capensis*. This can be explained because *Merluccius* are very closed related species and the number of discriminatory polymorphism is reduced. However, this is not a constraint since in Europe only one hake species is caught and therefore susceptible to be discarded.

According with the type of discards that we are likely to find mixtures of fish species in blocks, a batch of binary samples [HKE + COD] at different proportion were tested. Finally, we can conclude that the RPA Exo-assay is able to identify the presence of 5 % of HKE in a complex mixture of fish muscle (Figure 32B).

Figure 32. **(A1)** HKE specificity RPA Nfo-assay **(A2)** HKE specificity RPA Nfo-assay **(B)** HKE limit of detection RPA Nfo-assay with five binary samples. COD: *Gadus morhua*. HKE: *Merluccius merluccius*. POL: *Pollachius pollachius*. Test line (T); Internal Control line (C). Negative Template Control (NTC)

3.2.3 Fast DNA identification Kit prototype

For the use of the developed solution for the absence/presence of a specie in a fish mix a kit has been designed. Kit components are detailed in the Figure 7.

Figure 33. Lateral Flow Kit include: **(A)** cotton swab; **(B)** plastic pipettes **(C)** lateral flow. **(Tube 1)** DNA isolation Buffer; **(Tube 2)** Dilution buffer; **(Tube 3 &4)** RPA reactives; **(Tube 5)** Development buffer

The use of the kit is very simple and can be done by any person without further training. In brief the sample is taken with the cotton swab (A), introduced in the tube 1. Using the plastic pipettes (B) a sample is added to tube 2. A sample from tube 2 is taken with a new pipette and put into tube 3. The content of tube 4 is added to tube 3 and maintained at 35-40 °C for a specific amount of time.

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Finally, a sample of tube 3 is transferred with the last pipette to the tube 5, and the lateral flow strip is dipped in it.

The presence of a control mark will indicate that the process has been performed correctly and a second mark will appear if the tested specie is present in the mix.

3.3 Conclusion

Results confirm that RPA technology is suitable to discriminate Atlantic cod and European hake within 15 minutes (excluding DNA isolation) with an inexpensive, portable and very simple to use lateral flow system. This technology could be used in-, on-, by- or at-line in various locations of the food supply including fish vessels, harbours, fish markets, processors etc...